

Food4Future

Care about safe and sustainable food?

FoodSafety4EU

MULTI-STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM
FOR FOOD SAFETY IN EUROPE

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Credits

IDEA, EDITORIAL CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT AND EXECUTION

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Aquaponic farm Novak

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Do you care about the food choices you make?

For sure taste, cost and preference is important, but do you also think about reducing meat and dairy intake, reducing food waste, and focusing on local and seasonal food when you make food choices?

Eating locally grown, seasonal food can be a better choice for the environment, and for your health, too! Consider buying more locally grown food - such as vegetables and fish from aquaponic farms - and you'll be helping to eliminate the environmental cost of shipping vegetables and fish across the country, and often around the globe. You'll also be getting fresher and more nutritious food for yourself and your family!

Join Victoria and her mum, Jane, when they discover how important safe, nutritious and sustainable food is to them!

Want to know more about how safe food affects our climate, about circularity and aquaponics?

Check out www.foodsafety4.eu where you can find more information for yourself and share with your friends!

ALL CROPS NEED PROTECTION

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MODERN FARMING FOCUSES ON SAFETY AND SUSTAINABILITY

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THE MULTIPLE BENEFITS OF AQUAPONICS

HI JOHNNY!
LOOK, MUM! THIS
IS AQUAPONICS,
THE FUTURE OF
FARMING!

WELL, TO ME IT
LOOKS MORE LIKE
A FACTORY THAN A
FARM... DOESN'T SEEM
VERY NATURAL...

HAHA YOU'RE RIGHT!
COME WITH ME,
I'LL SHOW YOU,
EVERYTHING
IS NATURAL,
I PROMISE!

HERE WE GROW MORE THAN
20 TYPES OF LETTUCE, AND
WE CONTROL EVERYTHING
FROM LIGHT TO TEMPERATURE
AND NUTRIENTS!

EVERYTHING IS INSIDE, SO YOU
DON'T NEED ANY PESTICIDES?

NOT A SINGLE DROP! AND SINCE THEY GROW IN WATER
AND NOT IN SOIL, IT SAVES A LOT OF SPACE, WATER,
AND THERE IS ZERO POLLUTION!

IT'S REALLY SIMPLE! THE FISH GET
ADEQUATE NUTRIENTS AND THEN PRODUCE
NITRATES WHICH IS FOOD FOR LETTUCE.
THE WATER FLOW IS CLEANED AND
CONTROLLED, THE FISH ARE SWIMMING
ALL DAY, WITHOUT VETERINARY DRUGS,
EVERYONE IS HAPPY!

OK, BUT THE WHOLE FACTORY
MUST BE ENERGY INTENSIVE
WITH THE TANKS, THE LIGHT
AND EVERYTHING!

NOT AT ALL IF YOU COMPARE TO
TRADITIONAL FARMING: OUR FISH DON'T
REQUIRE BOATS OR HEATING, THE LETTUCE
DOESN'T NEED A TRACTOR, AND WE PRODUCE
EVERYTHING LOCALLY CLOSE TO THE CITIES,
SO LESS TRANSPORTATION!

WELL, THANKS SO MUCH FOR THE
VISIT AND FOR THE FRESH FISH,
JOHNNY! NEXT TIME WE INVITE
YOU TO OUR HOME SO YOU CAN
HELP US WITH OUR LETTUCE IN
THE BACKYARD!

MOM, COME ON, YOU KNOW
JOHNNY IS NOT A GARDENER! BUT
MAYBE HE CAN HELP INSTALL A TINY
FARM IN OUR BACKYARD!

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FOR FOOD SAFETY IN EUROPE

Include, shape, act!

FoodSafety4EU is a collaborative action to support the European Commission (EC) in shaping the **Food Safety System of the future**.

FoodSafety4EU will design, develop and release a **multi-stakeholder platform** with digital knowledge and tools to **help citizens, scientists, companies, EC, EFSA, and Food Safety Authorities** co-design and shape together the future Food Safety System in Europe.

JOIN OUR PLATFORM BY REGISTERING HERE

www.foodsafety4.eu

✉ Contact us at foodsafety4eu@apre.it

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